

Full Length Article

Correlations between tar content and permanent gases as well as reactor temperature in a lab-scale fluidized bed biomass gasifier applying different feedstock and operating conditions

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Fluidized bed
Biomass
Gasification
Tar correlations
Steam
Oxygen

ABSTRACT

The major problem of fluidized bed biomass gasification is the high tar contamination of the producer gas which is associated with the complex and time-consuming sampling and analysis of these tars. Therefore, correlations to predict the tar content are a helpful tool for the development and operation of biomass gasifiers. Correlations between tars and gas composition as well as reactor temperature derived for a steam-blown lab-scale bubbling fluidized bed gasifier are investigated in this study to assess their applicability. A comprehensive data set containing over 80 experimental points was obtained for various operation conditions, including variations in temperature from 700 to 800 °C, feedstock, amount of steam for fluidization, as well as the addition of oxygen. Linear correlations between tar and permanent gases show good accuracy for H₂ and CH₄ when using pure steam. However, experiments conducted with steam-oxygen mixtures show high deviations for the CH₄-based correlation and smaller but still significant deviations for the H₂-based correlation. No relation between tar and CO or CO₂ was found. The correlation between tar and temperature shows highest accuracy, including good agreement with the steam-oxygen experiments. All tar correlations showed useful results over a broad operating range. However, significant deviations can be obtained when considering just one gas compound. Therefore, a combination of different correlations considering gas components and temperature seems to be the best method of tar prediction. This leads to a powerful tool for fast online tar monitoring for a broad range of operating conditions, once a calibration measurement was conducted.

1. Introduction

In order to tackle global climate change and reduce CO₂ emissions, we need to prioritize renewable energy sources [1]. Biomass is already widely used for heat production via combustion, however the utilization of biomass via gasification is a very promising technology [2]. Still, this technology needs stronger economic incentives from the society and further development to reach a full commercial status and a broad implementation. Gasification leads to a producer gas applicable for a wide variety of uses like the production of power via a gas engine or a

fuel cell, but it can also be used to produce biofuels and chemicals.

The main reactor concepts used for biomass gasification are the entrained flow reactor, the fixed bed reactor, the fluidized bed reactor, the rotary kiln reactor and the plasma reactor [3]. While the entrained flow reactor is not very flexible regarding fuel size and moisture content, it produces a high-quality producer gas and is easy to scale-up which leads to low capital costs. Fluidized-bed reactors can deal with a wide range of fuel particle sizes and are well suited for large scale applications due to the vigorous mixing and therefore homogeneous conditions in the bed. However, main disadvantages are the limit of a lower operating

Abbreviations: db, dry basis; ER, equivalence ratio; FC, fixed carbon; GC, gas chromatography; M, moisture; MP, Miscanthus pellets; MS, mass spectrometry; SBR, steam to biomass ratio; SWP, softwood pellets; VM, volatile matter; wb, wet basis; WGSR, water gas shift reaction.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2021.121531>

Received 20 April 2021; Received in revised form 20 July 2021; Accepted 20 July 2021

Available online 29 July 2021

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temperature due to agglomerations caused by molten ash and comparably high operating costs. Fixed-bed gasifiers are categorized in updraft (solid material moves down and gas moves up, counter-current) and downdraft (solid material and gas move downwards, co-current) gasifiers. Fixed-bed updraft gasifiers are simple and robust but lead to a high tar content in the producer gas whereas downdraft gasifiers have low tar concentrations but are difficult to scale up and have a low fuel flexibility. In general, fixed-bed gasifiers are more suitable for small-scale combined heat and power applications. Rotary kiln and plasma gasifiers are not widespread due to the low syngas quality [3]. The present study will focus on fluidized bed reactors.

As gasification is an endothermic process, heat needs to be supplied to maintain the operating temperature in the gasification reactor. In an autothermal gasifier, the heat-of-reaction is supplied internally via partial combustion of the biomass using air, enriched air or O₂. This leads either to an unfavorable dilution of the producer gas with nitrogen or to higher operating costs due to the demand of pure oxygen. In an allothermal gasifier, the heat-of-reaction is supplied externally either via circulation of hot bed material between two separated reactors for gasification and combustion or via heat exchangers, which leads to a nitrogen-free producer gas. Usually, steam is used as gasification agent for allothermal reactor designs. This leads to a high calorific value producer gas but comes with the difficulty of energy supply to power the endothermic gasification reactions [4]. To produce biofuels or chemicals, large scales and a high calorific value of the producer gas are preferred. Therefore, the most suited types of reactor for these applications are based on allothermal gasification using steam or autothermal gasification employing a mixture of steam and oxygen, obtaining a producer gas with high calorific value. For this reason, the experiments conducted in this study are mainly conducted employing steam as well as mixtures of steam and oxygen.

Different fluidized bed reactor concepts are discussed by Karl and Pröll [5] in a comprehensive review about allothermal biomass steam gasification. They state that most of the reactor concepts developed currently are based on the dual fluidized bed technology, which is based on two fluidized bed reactors connected via loop seals allowing the exchange of particles between the two reactors without an exchange of gases [6]. Biomass is fed to the steam-blown gasification reactor, where syngas is produced. The bed material together with some of the char is then lead to the air-blown combustion reactor through the loop seal. The exothermic combustion of the char particles heats up the bed material, which is then fed back to the gasification reactor. This concept allows to split gasification and combustion to achieve a non-diluted high heating value producer gas at the expense of a rather complex reactor design. However, especially for waste gasification, technical challenges make it difficult to apply the technology commercially and further development of an advanced reactor concept is currently being performed [7,8]. Furthermore, despite the improvements of this technology in the past, tar contents are still relatively high when compared to a downdraft gasifier.

A different approach to achieve a non-diluted producer gas is based on a bubbling fluidized bed reactor while using a mixture of steam and O₂ or enriched air as fluidization agent [9,10]. While this reduces the technical complexity of the gasification facility, it comes with the downside of high costs of O₂. However, as water electrolysis will probably get more relevant for H₂ production as a storage medium for solar and wind power [11], the price of O₂, which is a byproduct of electrolysis, will also decrease.

The main limitation of the industrial use of biomass gasification is the presence of tars in the producer gas. Tars are a mixture of condensable organic compounds which hinder the use of the obtained gas in many applications like energy production via gas turbines, gas engines or fuel cells as well as chemical utilization [3]. Operating conditions and gasifier design strongly influence tar formation. Temperature, pressure, fluidizing agent and additives as well as the ratio of fluidizing agent to biomass feed are the most influential operating parameters [12].

Furthermore, gasifier design strongly influences the residence time and temperature gradients inside the bed and therefore fundamentally affects tar formation. A distinct impact on tar formation was found for catalytic ash layers on the olivine particles leading to a reduced tar content in the producer gas. Kirnbauer et al. [13] observed a significant decrease of tar and a lower energy demand when running tests with used olivine compared to totally fresh olivine. However, no specifications are given for the time needed to reach the state of fully activated bed material. Further, a detailed characterization of ash layers on olivine particles in fluidized bed biomass gasifiers was recently published by Kuba et al. [14]. The activation of olivine particles due to interaction with ash in the fluidized bed reactor after long-term operation showed an increase of the surface area due to Ca enrichment. The age of the used olivine particles however could not be distinctively determined which makes it difficult to estimate the timescale necessary to reach an activated condition of the olivine.

The tar content of the producer gas can be decreased either via in-situ measures, which are implemented inside the reactor, or by employing ex-situ measures with the help of down-stream gas cleaning units. A detailed review by Valderrama Rios et al. [12] gives a comprehensive overview of the reduction of tar generated during biomass gasification. Tar abatement methods were investigated using the experimental setup of the current study by Soria-Verdugo et al. [15] employing different bed materials (in-situ) and by Fuentes-Cano et al. [16] employing a down-stream char-bed at high temperatures (ex-situ). Further primary measures and their application in a novel reactor concept are discussed by Heidenreich and Foscolo in [17].

An additional difficulty presents the sampling and analysis of tars in the producer gas. The guideline presented in Neef et al. [18] based on tar condensation in a solvent is very helpful in order to achieve comparable results and to get a detailed knowledge of the tar composition when using GC-MS or GC-FID analysis. However, it is very time-consuming and complex and does not allow online measurement. Furthermore, expensive equipment is needed to conduct the analysis. An alternative tar sampling method based on solid phase adsorption (SPA) presented by Brage et al. [19] shows a similar problematic. In order to tackle this problem, studies investigating the correlation of the tar content with gas components which are more easy to measure are conducted in literature e.g. by Zachl et al. [20], Dufour et al. [21] and Benedikt et al. [22]. Such correlations would allow to facilitate the development of biomass gasifiers in relation to tar contaminants and also allow better online monitoring of industrial plants.

Zachl et al. [20] investigated the correlation between tar and the total hydrocarbon content measured using flame ionization detection in a fixed bed downdraft gasifier operated with air. They found an exponential function to show the best fit between gravimetric tars and total hydrocarbon content. Different operating conditions as well as two different types of fuel, softwood pellets and wood chips, were considered in the data set. However, it was shown that the correlation depends on the type of fuel and is expected to depend on specific gasifier conditions.

Dufour et al. [21] investigated gas and tar composition obtained via wood chips pyrolysis at 700 to 1000 °C. They found linear relations between molar concentration of benzene and CH₄ and between all quantified tars and C₂H₄. Therefore, they propose that CH₄ and C₂H₄ could be used for online monitoring of the tar content in a gasification reactor. They argue that due to the high temperatures of the pyrolysis experiments and low effects of H₂O on hydrocarbon thermal conversion, the correlations could also be valid for dual-fluidized-bed gasifiers.

Benedikt et al. [22] conducted measurements of gas components and tar in a pilot plant and at industrial-scale employing steam as fluidization agent in the gasification reactor of the dual fluidized bed. Good fitting non-linear correlations were found between tar content and H₂, CH₄ or C₂H₄, whereas no coherent correlations were found for CO or CO₂. Similar trends were found for the pilot and the industrial plant. Although slight changes in the operation conditions like temperature or pressure fluctuations are included in the correlations, the data set is

limited to one specific operation condition, fuel and fluidizing agent for each plant. Furthermore, the influence of different fluidization agents on the correlations was not investigated.

A recent study by Borgmeyer and Behrendt [23] further emphasizes the importance of fast online tar measurement tools suitable for long-term operation in biomass gasification plants. They demonstrate the operation of a robust tar measurement based on fluorescence which can run without interaction of the operator for several weeks, however additional complicated and expensive equipment is needed.

In this study, a comprehensive investigation of data collected over several years is presented and used to derive and assess correlations to predict the tar content in a lab-scale biomass gasifier based on permanent gases and temperature. Experimental results of gas composition and tar content obtained in a lab-scale bubbling fluidized bed gasifier are compared for different operating conditions. The influence of temperature was investigated between 700 and 800 °C. The effect of feedstock was examined using softwood and Miscanthus pellets. Furthermore, the use of steam to biomass ratio (SBR) from 0.55 to 1.65 as well as the use of steam-oxygen mixtures showed the impact of the fluidization agent on the producer gas. The results of this extensive study consisting of more than 80 experimental data points are then used to establish correlations between the tar content and the temperature in the freeboard of the reactor as well as correlations between tar content and gas components like CH₄ and H₂. This allows for an easy and low budget online estimation of tar content once a calibration measurement is conducted at a specific facility. These correlations are particularly interesting as the wide data set goes beyond conditions previously tested in other studies. Their applicability as well as limitations are thoroughly discussed in this work. Correlations which follow the same principles as the ones derived in this work help the improvement and operation of gasification facilities as they simplify and speed up the process of tar

determination and tar mitigation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental setup

The experiments presented in this study were conducted in a lab-scale fluidized bed gasifier located at Graz University of Technology. A schematic of the experimental rig is shown in Fig. 1.

The fluidized bed reactor made of stainless steel consists of a cylindrical bottom part with an inner diameter of 80 mm and a height of 150 mm. This is where the bed material is located. Above the bottom part, the reactor opens up in diameter from 80 to 250 mm in a conically shaped part of 80 mm height followed by another cylindrical part of 110 mm height. This upper part will be referred to as the freeboard. At the very bottom, a gas distributor in the center of the reactor is used to introduce the fluidizing agent, which can be mixtures of steam and oxygen. Steam is produced in a steam generator, whereas the required amount can be controlled via an orifice measurement and an automated valve. Oxygen is supplied through a gas bottle and controlled via a Vögtlin mass flow controller. The mixed gas stream is preheated to a temperature of 400 °C before it enters the bed. 900 g of olivine with a mean diameter of 260 μ m is used as bed material. The experimental minimal fluidization velocity of the olivine bed is 0.044 m/s. The reactor is electrically heated and can be operated up to a maximum temperature of 800 °C. The temperature is measured at six different heights in the center of the reactor. Thermocouples T₁ and T₂ are located inside the bed, T₃ is in the transition zone and T₄ to T₆ are located in the freeboard. The mean value of T₁, T₂ and T₃ is used to control the electric heating of the oven in order to reach the desired operating temperature. Biomass feedstock is delivered to the bed from the top. An intermittently

Fig. 1. Schematic of the experimental set-up.

operated screw feeder is used to determine the amount of fuel which falls on the top of the bed. In order to adjust the feeding rate, the rotation velocity of the screw as well as the interval of pause- and rotation-time can be adjusted. A pneumatic air lock located just after the feeding screw as well as a constant nitrogen mass-flow of 0.15 kg/h to the fuel tank prevent the producer gas from reaching the feedstock. This is especially important when using pelletized material as the moist producer gas will lead to decomposition of the pellets and a blockage of the feeding system. The gaseous products obtained in the fluidized bed leave the reactor at the top and are led to a sinter metal candle filter to remove elutriated particles. All downstream pipes as well as the filter are heated to a temperature of 350 °C in order to avoid tar condensation. A pressure regulator after the filter keeps the pressure in the system at 2 bar.

Part of the gas is then lead to the tar sampling system which is based on the tar guideline [18]. The gas runs through five impinger bottles filled with 100 ml isopropanol in order to condense most of the tars. The impinger bottles are placed in two thermostats operated at 40 °C and -20 °C as shown in Fig. 1. An additional bottle filled with glass beads is placed at the end to ensure a solvent free gas for downstream equipment. After the sampling period of 30 to 40 min, the isopropanol is collected and can then be analyzed by either a gravimetric method to determine the absolute amount of tars or by GC-MS analysis, in order to get further insight of its chemical composition. After the tar sampling bottles, the producer gas goes through a membrane pump which creates the under-pressure needed to overcome the pressure difference of the frits and the liquid-column in the impinger bottles. A gas flow meter is used to determine the exact amount of dry gas at standard ambient temperature and pressure (298.15 K and 1.013 bar). Thereafter, the producer gas composition is analyzed in an ABB AO2020 gas analyzer, which measures the concentration of CO, CO₂, CH₄, H₂ and O₂. The producer gas is then burned in a flare using a methane burner in order to achieve total combustion before it is led to the atmosphere via a chimney. The isopropanol collected for each test during the tar sampling is afterwards analyzed using the gravimetric method. This results in a gravimetric tar content which is related to the amount of dry syngas at standard ambient temperature and pressure measured by the mass flow meter. A selection of the tar samples is analyzed in a gas-chromatograph mass-spectrometer detector (GC-MS: HP G1800C GCD, Agilent) using a capillary column (VF-5 ms, 30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm) and He as carrier gas. A list of the 20 species analyzed can be found in the supplementary material. For quantitative characterization, each species was calibrated individually using pure compounds with different concentrations. Furthermore, an internal standard (guaiaicol, not detected in any of the samples) was introduced in the external standards, as well as in the samples, aiming at correcting deviations in the results derived from variations in the injection amount, bypass flow, etc.

2.1.1. Biomass

Softwood pellets, representative of woody biomass, and Miscanthus pellets, representative of agricultural and herbaceous biomass, are used as feedstock in the experiments conducted during this study. The proximate analysis as well as the ultimate analysis for the two types of biomass are presented in Table 1. The main difference is a lower fixed carbon content for the softwood pellets and a significantly higher ash content for Miscanthus. The diameter of the cylindrical pellets was about 6 mm for softwood and 9 mm for Miscanthus pellets. The density was measured as 1175 kg/m³ for softwood pellets and 899 kg/m³ for

Miscanthus pellets. The rigidity of the Miscanthus pellets was observed to be a lot more brittle compared to the softwood pellets which might lead to increased attrition.

2.2. Operating conditions

The operating conditions of all experimental cases are presented in Table 2. About 50 measurements have been conducted at reference operating conditions (Ref.) where the gasifier is operated at a bed temperature of 750 °C using softwood pellets as feedstock. The biomass feeding rate is about 0.255 kg/h, which corresponds to a thermal power input of about 1.3 kW. The steam mass flow is set to 0.280 kg/h which results in a steam to biomass ratio of 1.1. Based on the reference case, the influence of temperature on the gasification process was investigated changing the bed temperature to 700 °C (T-) and 800 °C (T+) while keeping the other parameters constant. The typical reactor temperature of allothermal biomass gasifiers given by Karl and Pröll [5] ranges from 670 to 900 °C. Therefore, a variation of temperature was conducted including operating temperatures of 700, 750 and 800 °C. Experiments conducted at even higher temperatures would be of high relevance. However, tests above 800 °C were not possible due to temperature limitations of the reactor setup used in this study. In the case of 800 °C, biomass feeding was slightly higher due to a small irregularity in the feeding system. The influence of the amount of steam was studied using a steam mass flow of 0.14 kg/h (S-) and 0.42 kg/h (S+). The tests using Miscanthus (Misc.) as fuel were conducted at the same reactor settings as for the reference case. The feeding system was adjusted to achieve the desired feeding rate as Miscanthus pellets differed in size and density from the softwood pellets. Further tests were conducted using a mixture of steam and oxygen as fluidizing agent (O₂/S). The reactor was run at a slightly higher fuel feeding rate of 0.374 kg/h corresponding to a fuel power input just below 2 kW. To achieve optimal conditions in autothermal biomass gasification in a fluidized bed, Ren et al. [24] suggest an equivalence ratio (ER) range between 0.2 and 0.3, similar to the range of 0.2 to 0.4 given by Bates et al. [25]. Therefore, the amount of oxygen used in this study was determined to achieve an ER of 0.18, 0.23 and 0.28 which corresponds to 0.091, 0.115 and 0.138 kg/h of O₂, respectively.

2.3. Operating procedure

All tests in this study were conducted in the experimental rig described above. A similar routine for all tests ensures the comparability of the results. For each operation condition, the measurement routine was repeated multiple times in order to get a comprehensive set of data. As the gasifier was regularly in operation to produce a syngas for the investigation of gas cleaning with secondary measures or gas utilization e.g. in a solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC), a broad data set including many repetitions could be obtained. Prior to each measurement, the reactor was run for at least 3 h to ensure that a constant gas composition and tar content was reached. This relatively long time required to achieve constant conditions in the reactor can be partly explained by the rather slow reactor control system, which is optimized for stable operation rather than the fast changes which occur during the start-up phase. Furthermore, the amount of char present in the reactor builds up during this time to a certain value. Long term experiments conducted over several days have shown that this value stays almost constant once an

Table 1

Characterization of softwood and Miscanthus pellets (M: Moisture, VM: Volatile Matter, FC: Fixed Carbon, m%: percentage by mass, wb: wet basis, db: dry basis, *: difference to 100%).

Fuel	M (m%wb)	VM (m%wb)	FC (m%wb)	C (m%db)	H (m%db)	O* (m%db)	N (m%db)	S (m%db)	Ash (m%db)
Softwood pellets	7.3	78.8	13.9	49.5	6.6	43.4	0.1	< 0.1	0.3
Miscanthus pellets	10.4	70.7	18.9	49.0	6.0	42.3	0.5	< 0.1	2.1

Table 2

Comparison of different operating conditions. SWP: softwood pellets, MP: Miscanthus pellets, ER: equivalence ratio, SBR: steam to biomass ratio.

Case	Num. Exp. (-)	Fuel (-)	Bed Temperature (°C)	Biomass feeding (kg/h)	Steam feeding (kg/h)	ER (-)	SBR (-)
Ref.	46	SWP	750	0.255	0.280	0	1.10
T-	4	SWP	700	0.255	0.280	0	1.10
T+	2	SWP	800	0.270	0.280	0	1.04
S-	6	SWP	750	0.255	0.140	0	0.55
S+	8	SWP	750	0.255	0.420	0	1.65
Misc.	7	MP	750	0.289	0.280	0	0.97
O ₂ /S	10	SWP	750	0.374	0.469	0 / 0.18 / 0.23 / 0.28	1.25

equilibrium is reached. Ash accumulation in the bed is assumed to have minor influences on the process as the formation of ash is below 1 g/h when employing softwood pellets having a low ash content of 0.3 % combined with a rather low fuel feeding of below 300 g/h. Operation conditions when employing Miscanthus lead to about 5 g/h of ash which is not negligible. However, it was seen that the standard deviation of tars and gas composition of these experiments is rather low (lower than for the cases using softwood with lower amounts of ash). Furthermore, we believe that most small ash particles are elutriated from the bed as ash accumulation could not be observed during the service and maintenance periods of the reactor. As already stated in the introduction, activation of olivine particles due to coating with an catalytic ash layer leads to a significant decrease of the tar content when compared to fresh olivine [13,14]. However, as used (and therefore already activated) olivine is employed for all cases in the current study, it is assumed that the catalytic activity of the ash layer was almost constant.

The individual measurements were conducted at different times after the start of the reactor operation, which might lead to small deviations and partly explains the variability of the results. As this increases the diversity of the measurement data, however, it does not pose a problem but rather leads to a broader data base for development of the tar correlations. After constant conditions in the gasifier were ensured by checking temperature and gas composition, the sampling of tars was conducted for 30 to 40 min. Therefore, part of the gas was lead through the condensation setup described above. Simultaneously, the permanent gases were determined via the gas analysis. At the beginning of the experimental study, most sampling periods were conducted for 40 min. However, it was observed later on that a measurement period of 30 min leads to the same result with similar accuracy and reproducibility at a smaller time cost.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Comparison of different operating conditions using steam as fluidizing agent

First, general differences in the gas composition regarding tar content as well as gas components for all cases using pure steam as fluidizing agent are investigated. The results for cases using a mixture of steam and oxygen (O₂/S) are discussed separately later on. Fig. 2 shows averaged measurement results with corresponding standard deviations for the operating points described in Table 2. The values shown are calculated as the average of all individual measurements conducted for the respective operation condition. The gravimetric tar content measured for the reference case is 8.6 ± 2.2 g/m³. Increasing the mean bed temperature by 50 °C to a value of 800 °C (T+), the amount of tars is about half as big, whereas a decrease of temperature by 50 °C to 700 °C (T-) leads to about the double amount of tars. This general dependency of the tar content on temperature is a well-known fact and is already well documented in literature for lab-scale biomass gasification [26] as well as for industrial-scale dual fluidized bed gasification plants [27]. When reducing the amount of steam as for case S-, the tar content increases to a higher value of about 18 g/m³ similar as for the case at 700 °C. At S-, the

Fig. 2. Comparison of producer gas for different operating conditions.

decreased amount of fluidization media seems to influence the fluid dynamics of the bed and leads to a decrease in mixing. This is probably also the reason for the significant change of the temperature profile along the reactor height, showing a difference of top and bottom temperature of almost 60 °C compared to 35 °C for the reference case, and will be further discussed later on in this chapter. Altogether, the decrease in mixing and the change of temperature profile leads to an increase in tars. An increase in the amount of steam as in case S+ leads to a more vigorous fluidization and shows a tar content of 6.7 ± 3.5 g/m³, slightly lower than for the reference case. Karl and Pröll [5] also state that additional steam reduces tars due to reforming reactions and improves the producer gas quality. Miscanthus experiments show about twice the tar content compared to softwood at the same bed temperature, resulting in 15.7 ± 1.7 g/m³. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no direct comparison of the tar content of the product gas obtained by gasification of softwood and Miscanthus in the same plant has been presented in the literature so far. Myrén et al. [28] presented tar contents of pyrolysis gas from birch, Miscanthus and straw after thermal cracking at 700, 850 and 900 °C. When comparing the total light aromatics excluding benzene, the tar content using Miscanthus was almost twice as big compared to birch for all temperatures. Although the gas was obtained via pyrolysis and results after a thermal tar cracking unit are presented in Myrén et al. [28], the comparison of gas obtained with Miscanthus as feedstock shows a similar magnitude as in the present study.

The standard deviation of the tar measurement, as shown in Fig. 2, is significantly higher compared to the permanent gases. This can be attributed partly to the fact that the operation of the gasifier is not perfectly constant due to small irregularities in fuel and steam feeding and small fluctuations of the reactor heating. This can subsequently lead to small changes of temperature in the bed as well as in the freeboard which then influences formation and cracking of tars. Furthermore, these temperature changes and fluctuations of steam feeding can also lead to slight differences in the amount of char present in the bed, which is also affecting the tar content of the produced gas. However, the effect of short irregularities in temperature and fluidization conditions on the char content is expected to be rather small as the amount of char in the

bed changes very slowly. As already mentioned above, the different operation times of the individual measurements can attribute to the variability within one operation condition. However, as this leads to a broader set of measurement points available for the assessment of tar correlations, this is not a disadvantage. Additionally, the complexity and error-proneness of the sampling and analysis method further discussed in Neef et al. [18] could also increase the standard deviation.

When looking at the permanent gases in Fig. 2, a producer gas composition typical for steam gasification in a bubbling fluidized bed can be observed (see also Table 3). For the temperature variation, CO₂ and CO stay almost constant and show no clear trend. However, the influence of the amount of steam on CO and CO₂ is clearly visible. More steam leads to an increase of CO₂ and a decrease in CO due to the water gas shift reaction (WGSR). Miscanthus experiments show similar values for CO and CO₂ compared to the reference case. The amount of CH₄ shows a subtle dependency on temperature and the amount of steam. At temperatures above the reference case (T+) as well as for higher amounts of steam (S+), a small decrease of CH₄ can be seen. At lower temperatures (T-) and when using less steam (S-), more CH₄ is found in the producer gas. The results for Miscanthus show a slightly higher CH₄ concentration when compared with the experiments using softwood pellets. Completely opposite trends are found when investigating the H₂ content. Lower temperatures as well as low amounts of steam lead to a decrease in H₂, whereas higher temperatures and more steam increase the H₂ content of the producer gas. The use of Miscanthus instead of softwood pellets leads to a gas with about 5 % less H₂.

A comparison of the gas composition at the reference point with data from literature is presented in Table 3. To make the data easier to compare, the nitrogen free gas composition is shown. Karl and Pröll [5] present a typical range of the syngas obtained in a steam-blown bubbling bed biomass gasifier. Bates et al. [25] conducted experiments in a lab-scale fluidized bed gasifier operating at very similar conditions as the reference point used in this study. Using a bubbling bed gasifier fluidized with steam at a bed temperature of 750 °C and a SBR of 1, the main differences are a smaller particle size, the use of hardwood fuel and a lower reactor pressure. Further results of biomass gasification conducted in a bubbling fluidized bed gasifier using softwood pellets as fuel were presented by Mayerhofer et al. [29]. Operation at different reactor temperatures, pressures and SBRs leads to a range for the gas composition, whereas all results of the present study lie within this range. Tars were measured using a different method based on solid phase adsorption and are therefore not directly comparable. Additionally, typical results obtained in a dual-fluidized bed gasifier by Pfeifer et al. [30] are shown. It can be seen that, although a different reactor technology is used, the gas composition of the current study lies within the ranges of this facility. The results measured in the present study are either within the ranges given in literature or very close to upper or lower limit. This ensures that a gas composition representative for bubbling fluidized bed biomass gasification was obtained with the lab scale reactor used in this study. Based on the discussion in the previous paragraph, the trends obtained for variations in operation conditions are as well in line with

literature. The trends for gas components and tar content due to increasing amount of steam are same as presented by Herguido et al. [31]. Temperature trends are discussed by Bates et al. [25] for a bubbling fluidized bed and by Kuba and Hofbauer [27] for dual fluidized bed gasification. The general trends observed in the present paper are well in-line with literature. However, the clear trends showing decreasing CO and increasing CO₂ when increasing the temperature could not be seen, which is probably related to the overall lower temperature range with a maximum of 800 °C applied in this study. Both papers point out the importance of the water gas shift equilibrium coefficient. At low temperatures, the formation of H₂ and CO₂ is favoured, however, above 800 °C the direction of the reaction changes which favours the production of CO and H₂O. However, as these conditions lead to faster kinetics, the equilibrium is more likely to be reached at high temperatures. This topic is discussed in more depth by Kuba et al. [32]. Bates et al. state that higher temperatures promote heterogeneous char gasification kinetics which leads to a higher H₂ content, which was also observed in this study.

In order to better understand the influence of temperature on the gasification process, the temperature field in the reactor is shown in Fig. 3. The temperatures for each operation condition are averaged values of all individual tests at different heights of the reactor. In total, six thermocouples are placed in the reactor. Thermocouple T₁ and T₂ are inside the bed, T₃ is in the transition zone between bed and freeboard and T₄ to T₆ are located in the freeboard (see Fig. 1). The reference case is operated at a mean bed temperature (average value of T₁, T₂ and T₃) of 750 °C. The temperature profile for this case shows a slightly lower temperature of 740 °C in the bottom of the bed and a temperature increase up to about 780 °C at T₄. Higher up in the reactor, the temperature drops slowly until T₅ followed by a strong decrease below 500 °C at T₆ due to thermal losses. The bed temperature at the bottom, T₁, is about 35 °C colder than at the top of the bed, T₃. The lower bed temperature at the lowest bed position can be explained by the energy

Fig. 3. Temperature distribution along the reactor height. Average of all cases for each operating condition.

Table 3

Comparison of N₂ free gas composition with typical range presented by Karl and Pröll [5], experimental results by Bates et al. [25] and Mayerhofer et al. [29]. Additional typical results obtained in a dual-fluidized bed gasifier by Pfeifer et al. [30] are given for comparison.

		This Study (N ₂ free)	Karl and Pröll [5]	Bates et al. [25]	Mayerhofer et al. [29]	Pfeifer et al. [30]
Temp	(°C)	750	–	750	750–840	850–900
Biomass	(-)	Softwood pellets (6 mm)	–	Hardwood (0.725 – 2 mm)	Softwood pellets (8 mm)	Wood pellets
SBR	(-)	1.1	–	1	0.8 – 1.2	0.5 – 1.2
Pressure	(bar)	2	–	1.17	1 – 2.5	Close to atmospheric
Bed material	(-)	Olivine	–	Olivine	Olivine	Olivine
CO ₂	(vol%db)	22.9	20–24	20.4	19–27	20–25
CO	(vol%db)	20.8	19–23	22.2	12–22	19–24
CH ₄	(vol%db)	8.8	9–12	8	6–10	9–12
H ₂	(vol%db)	45	36–41	42.6	38–48	36–42
Tars	(g/m ³)	8.6	3–8	not stated	2 – 6 (SPA-GC, excl. unknown)	4–8

needed to heat the steam to operating temperature and increased losses at the lower part of the reactor. T_4 is the hottest point in the freeboard for all cases. Together with the increased residence time in the wider freeboard region, this makes T_4 the most relevant temperature for tar cracking and other homogeneous gas phase reactions. For case T-, representing a mean reactor temperature of 700 °C, the temperature is very homogeneous throughout the reactor height until T_6 , where a significant drop below 500 °C, similar as for the reference case, can be observed. Case T+ operates at a mean temperature of 800 °C and shows a more homogeneous temperature profile in the whole reactor when compared to the reference case. The decrease of temperature in the bed at T_2 might be attributed to the increased endothermic char gasification reactions taking place in the mid and upper part of the bed. Using a lower amount of steam (S-) seems to inverse the tendencies in the bed observed for the reference case with a hotter bottom part and relatively cold freeboard. This might be partly attributed to the fact that light char particles tend to float at top of the bed and are less likely to reach the bottom when employing low fluidization velocities due to reduced vertical mixing. Consequently, this leads to less endothermic gasification reactions and therefore higher temperatures at the reactor bottom. For S+, a similar temperature gradient as for the reference case was observed. A slightly lower temperature at T_2 might be attributed to the more vigorous mixing due to increased amount of fluidization media which allows light biomass and char particles to penetrate deeper into the bed. Tests conducted using Miscanthus as fuel (Misc.) show a different trend compared to the reference case, showing a lower temperature at T_3 compared to T_2 and T_4 . Although both cases operate at the same mean bed temperature of 750 °C, it is difficult to directly compare these results as the Miscanthus pellets show different size and density compared to the softwood pellets which leads to different hydrodynamic behavior in the bed. The lower density of the Miscanthus pellets might lead to an increased bed height. The light char particles often found floating at the top of the bed can then lead to the temperature drop at T_3 due to the endothermic char gasification reactions.

3.2. Using steam-oxygen mixtures as fluidizing agent

When employing steam-oxygen mixtures, the amount of oxygen is crucial in order to maintain the desired temperature without burning too much of the producer gas. The equivalence ratio (ER) describes the ratio of the actual amount of oxygen used to the amount needed for stoichiometric combustion, similar to the air ratio used to characterize combustion processes. In an industrial facility, the ER determines the operating temperature. However, in the lab-scale reactor used in this study, the operating temperature can be chosen independently from ER due to the electrical heating. Schmid et al. [33] calculated an ER of 0.25 to achieve autothermal gasification under the assumption of adiabatic conditions and an operating temperature of 850 °C. Ren et al. [24] state an optimal ER between 0.2 and 0.3 for fluidized bed gasifiers. In this study, four cases were investigated using ER = 0, ER = 0.18, ER = 0.23 and ER = 0.28 to examine the influence of oxygen. The mean power input of the electric reactor was measured as 2.9 kW, 1.6 kW, 1.3 kW and 1.2 kW respectively, while the average estimated heat losses for this reactor are of 2.1, 1.4, 1.3 and 1.3 kW for each case respectively. This shows that for ER = 0.23 and ER = 0.28, the reactor is already running in autothermal mode, with electrical heating still necessary to compensate for heat losses. The gas composition and corresponding tar contents for the O₂/S cases are shown in Fig. 4. While in this case the fuel and steam input are slightly higher, operation with pure steam leads to similar results as the reference case (shown in Fig. 2) with a slightly higher hydrogen concentration which can be explained by the higher amount of steam that enhances WGSR. When adding oxygen, a significant change of tar content can be observed. The amount of tars is four to five times higher and shows a maximum for the intermediate value of ER = 0.23. This effect can most likely be explained by the changing temperature distribution in the reactor shown in Fig. 5. While the profile for ER = 0 is

Fig. 4. Comparison of producer gas for different operating conditions.

Fig. 5. Temperature distribution along the reactor height. Average of all cases for each operating condition.

very similar to the reference case (shown in Fig. 3), the tendencies are the opposite for experiments using additional oxygen showing a very hot bed and a cold freeboard. This can be explained by the fast combustion of char in the bed, which consumes most of the oxygen as described by Bates et al. [25]. At the same time, the need for electric heating is reduced which leads to lower temperatures in the freeboard, as most oxygen has already reacted in the lower part of the reactor. For ER = 0.18, the temperature in T_4 is about 100 °C lower when compared to ER = 0, which has a huge impact on thermal tar cracking reactions in this region. The temperature in T_4 for ER = 0, ER = 0.18, ER = 0.23 and ER = 0.28 are approximately 800 °C, 700 °C, 650 °C and 670 °C respectively. This drastic change of temperature distribution which leads to a relatively cold freeboard region with increasing ER is the main driver of the high tar contents encountered during these tests. However, this result is mainly related to the specific design of the lab scale reactor utilized in this study which employs an electric heating when running in allothermal but also in autothermal mode in order to maintain the target operating temperature. Therefore, these results cannot be directly transferred to industrial units. The slight increase of T_4 for ER = 0.28 might be explained by partly combustion of the syngas in the upper part of the reactor due to the increased amount of oxygen.

The mean gas composition measured for each of the four cases is presented in Fig. 4. For higher ERs, CO₂ shows an increasing concentration due to enhanced combustion reactions of char and CO. In contrast, CO and H₂ show decreasing trends as they are reactants of combustion reactions. There is no clear trend for CH₄. H₂ shows a significant decrease from ER = 0 to ER = 0.18 but is only slightly decreasing when adding more oxygen. This might be explained by the fact that many small char particles are combusted instead of gasified. Additionally, this effect can also be partly attributed to oxidation of hydrogen, which in general shows fast combustion kinetics compared to CO or CH₄ [25,34].

Similar experiments were conducted by Bates et al. [25] gasifying

oak particles at 850 °C in a bubbling fluidized bed employing mixtures of steam and air resulting in ER = 0, ER = 0.052, ER = 0.104 and ER = 0.157. Same trends were found for CO₂ showing a constant increase for higher ERs. Furthermore, the drastic drop of H₂ concentration when employing just a small amount of oxygen followed by only a slight decrease of H₂ when further increasing the ER are observed in both studies. However, it has to be mentioned that in the study of Bates et al. this effect is partly explained by the fact that they reduce steam feeding when adding air to maintain the superficial gas velocity constant. In contrast to the results presented in this study, Bates et al. found a significant increase of CO when increasing ER from 0 to 0.052 which they attribute to the additional char oxidation. For an increase of the ER beyond 0.052, they found an almost constant CO concentration which they explain by enhanced CO combustion balancing the additional char oxidation. The total tar content measured by Bates et al. via a molecular beam mass spectrometer is increasing when adding an incremental amount of oxygen at ER = 0.052, but then decreases again for ER = 0.104. Overall, the changes of tar content are much subtler and in the range of 10 % compared to 500 % measured in the present study. Bates et al. state that rather than destroying tars, it appears that the oxygen shifts the tar composition from lighter PAH's to heavier ones. This might contribute to the distinct tar increase measured in the present study as the gravimetric method has difficulties in measuring lighter tar compounds.

Further gasification experiments in an atmospheric bubbling fluidized bed are presented by Gil et al. [35]. The permanent gas composition as well as tar content of the gas was analyzed employing pure steam, steam-oxygen mixtures or air. When just looking at the test conducted with steam-oxygen mixtures, similar trends for the permanent gases were found as in the present study. As the ER was increased, they found an increase of CO₂, whereas CO and H₂ decreased significantly and CH₄ showed a slight decrease. Gil et al. found highest tar loadings using pure steam, followed by steam-oxygen mixtures. Lowest tar contents were achieved using air. However, Gil et al. point out that tar composition strongly affects the possibility to reduce the tar content with additional measures and states tars from steam gasification are more “easy to destroy” compared to tars obtained via air gasification.

3.3. Tar correlations

In the following chapter, relations between tar and gas components as well as tar and freeboard temperature are investigated. When possible, linear fits are established and their accuracy is assessed.

3.3.1. Correlation of gravimetric tar and methane

Figure 6 shows individual measurement results of gravimetric tar

Fig. 6. Gravimetric tar plotted against dry volumetric percentage of CH₄ in the producer gas for different operating conditions. Linear fit calculated without considering tests using O₂.

compared to the corresponding CH₄ content in the dry producer gas obtained for all different operating conditions. When not considering the O₂ case, a clear linear trend of increasing tar content for increasing CH₄ can be seen. The linear fit without considering the experiments using O₂ shows a coefficient of determination R² of about 0.70. Despite the good agreement for all of the other experiments, it is obvious that this correlation is not applicable for the O₂ cases as it would lead to a significant underestimation of tars. It is also notable that this correlation works well for tests conducted using either softwood or Miscanthus as fuel.

3.3.2. Correlation of gravimetric tar and hydrogen

A clear linear trend of decreasing tars for increasing H₂ content can be seen in Fig. 7. Cases at 800 °C (T+) and the use of high amounts of steam (S+) show favorable conditions for steam reforming reactions and therefore less tar contamination. Although less than in the case of the methane correlation, the O₂ experiments show significant deviation of this trend and were not considered during the calculation of the fit. The fit shows a coefficient of determination R² of 0.82, significantly higher than the methane correlation.

3.3.3. Influence of CO₂ and CO on gravimetric tar content

As can be seen in Fig. 8, there is no clear effect of CO₂ and CO on the tar content. As already observed above, the addition of oxygen leads to an increase of CO₂ visible in Fig. 8.a. A similar result showing no clear correlation of CO₂ and CO with the tar content was also obtained by Benedikt et al. [22].

3.3.4. Correlation of gravimetric tar and temperature

The strong influence of operating temperature on the tar content is a well-known fact [5,36,37]. Especially the freeboard temperature as well as the residence time of the gas in the freeboard have major influence on the tar content, as this is the place where steam reforming and tar cracking reactions take place. An investigation of the reactor temperature profiles has shown that T₄ is the most representative freeboard temperature as it shows the highest temperatures in the freeboard for all cases (see Fig. 3 and Fig. 5). Therefore, values measured at T₄ are used for the following evaluation. However, a representative position for the temperature measurement needs to be found individually for each reactor. A clear trend of decreasing tar with increasing freeboard temperature T₄ can be seen in Fig. 9. A linear fit shows very good accuracy for all cases, including the O₂ experiments, which showed significant deviation for the fits using gas components like CH₄ or H₂. A coefficient of determination R² of 0.83 can be achieved, which shows the best accuracy found in this study. Although the results are very good for all cases using softwood pellets as fuel, the tests using Miscanthus pellets show higher deviations from the correlation. Considering only the

Fig. 7. Gravimetric tar plotted against dry volumetric percentage of H₂ in the producer gas for different operating conditions. Linear fit calculated without considering tests using O₂.

Fig. 8. Gravimetric tar plotted against dry volumetric percentage of a) CO₂ and b) CO in the producer gas for different operating conditions.

Fig. 9. Gravimetric tar plotted against freeboard temperature T₄ for different operating conditions. Linear fit calculated considering all tests (including O₂/S).

Miscanthus cases, no clear trend between tar and temperature can be seen, as the temperature range studied is probably too small. However, these results seem to fulfill the correlation with acceptable accuracy, but show a slight shift towards higher tar concentrations compared to the cases where softwood is used as fuel. A significant influence of biomass composition on tar yield was also observed by Horvat et al. [37].

3.3.5. Correlation between methane and hydrogen

Gas composition measurement results of hydrogen plotted over methane are shown in Fig. 10. A distinct linear relation between H₂ and

Fig. 10. Correlation between H₂ and CH₄.

CH₄ can be seen. As CH₄ increases, the H₂ content decreases. CH₄ is favored at low temperatures and low amounts of steam whereas high temperatures and increased steam leads to more H₂ and a decrease in CH₄ which can partly be attributed to methane reforming [38]. However, data points obtained using steam-oxygen mixtures show a strong deviation and are not considered when calculating the fit. The addition of oxygen to the fluidizing agent seems to lead to strong decrease of H₂ due to partial combustion. A much higher reduction in H₂ content than CH₄ content can be seen, which is in accordance to literature (see section 3.2). That means that a correlation based on a single gas compound can be misleading, and it should be combined with a temperature measurement to be on the safe side when gasifiers are operated in a broad range of conditions.

3.3.6. Correlations based on tar determined via GC-MS

Representative tar samples of each operation condition were further analyzed using gas chromatography in order to better understand the tar composition and to check if tar correlations can also be found for the GC-MS tar results. Five samples were analyzed for case Ref., two samples for case Misc. and one sample for all other cases. Regarding the steam-oxygen mixtures, only the case employing ER = 0.23 was investigated. To get a better understanding of the tar composition, a classification of tars [39] in benzene, class 2, class 3, class 4 and class 5 was conducted and is presented in Table 4. Gravimetric tar results based on

Table 4 Comparison of gravimetric with GC tars and classification of GC tars.

		Ref.	T-	T+	S-	S+	O ₂ /S ER = 0.23	Misc.
Grav. tars (all samples)	(g/m ³)	7.6	18.8	4.0	17.7	6.7	30.6	15.7
Grav. tars (GC samples)	(g/m ³)	7.1	21.3	4.3	20.6	4.2	33.1	18.7
GC tars (excl. benzene)	(g/m ³)	6.1	12.9	3.8	13.5	3.9	10.5	13.7
Benzene	(g/m ³)	7.8	5.6	7.4	7.2	5.1	3.1	8.5
Class 2 (heterocyclic aromatics)	(g/m ³)	0.9	4.5	0.3	3.8	0.5	5.4	4.3
Class 3 (light aromatics, 1 ring)	(g/m ³)	2.0	4.5	1.0	4.4	1.1	3.8	4.8
Class 4 (light PAH compounds, 2-3 rings)	(g/m ³)	3.2	3.8	2.5	5.0	2.2	1.3	4.5
Class 5 (heavy PAH compounds, >3 rings)	(g/m ³)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1

all samples show that the samples selected for GC analysis are representative for each case. However, for S+, one of the samples with a rather low tar content was chosen for the analysis. When comparing the summed GC tars without benzene to the gravimetric results of the GC samples, relatively good agreement can be found for cases Ref., T+ and S+. Furthermore, it can be seen, that class 4 tars (light PAH compounds) make up for the largest part of the tars followed by class 3 tars (light aromatics, 1 ring). However, cases T-, S-, ER = 0.23 and Misc., all showing lower temperatures in the freeboard (see Fig. 3 and Fig. 4), lead to higher deviations between GC tars (excluding benzene) and gravimetric tars. A similar trend is reported by Fuentes-Cano et al. [40] were high deviations between gravimetric tars and GC tars (without BTX) were found at low temperatures and better agreement was found for temperatures above 750 °C. Benzene is not considered in this comparison, as it is assumed it is not captured when using the gravimetric method [33,41]. It can further be seen that in these cases, the share of class 2 tars (heterocyclic aromatics) is much higher. A similar trend was also observed by Katsaros et al. [42] who detected more oxygenated tars at lower temperatures when conducting GC analysis of tars produced in a bubbling fluidized bed reactor. The differences between GC and gravimetric tars for this low temperature cases can be explained to a certain extent by the much higher presence of non-calibrated class 3 tars or class 1 tars (GC undetectable).

Correlations of GC tars (excl. benzene) and CH₄, H₂ as well as temperature T₄ are presented in Fig. 11. As for the correlations based on gravimetric tars, the case employing oxygen is not considered for correlations based on permanent gases. Both correlations show similar coefficients of determination as for gravimetric tars when employing a linear fit. Benedikt et al. [22] found an exponential fit to show highest coefficients of determination when developing a correlation between GC–MS tars and H₂. When looking on the correlation based on temperature in Fig. 11.c, the case employing a steam-oxygen mixture does not show good agreement with the linear fit. Therefore, unlike the correlation based on gravimetric tars and temperature, it was not considered when establishing the correlation. This is probably linked to the inability of GC analysis to detect a significant fraction of the gravimetric tars, which are more relevant in this case. Linear correlations for specific tar classes based on CH₄, H₂ and temperature can be found in the supplementary material. They show that class 2 and 3 tars are easier to reduce when increasing the temperature and show stronger dependencies on CH₄ or H₂ concentrations. In general, good correlations were found for both GC and gravimetric analysis, which strengthens the general findings of the study. However, the GC analysis is more challenging for samples obtained at low temperatures with a higher extent of secondary tars and leads to a strong deviation for the temperature correlation employing GC-tars in the oxygen case, in contrast to the temperature correlation employing gravimetric tars. The following part of the paper will focus on the gravimetric results, as more data points are available.

3.4. Evaluation and discussion of correlations for gravimetric tars

The attained correlations to predict the tar content are now compared and assessed in order to find the best way to predict the tar content in the gasifier used for this study. Fig. 12 shows the calculated amount of tars plotted against the actually measured amount of tar for all three correlations for gravimetric tars obtained above. In the case of an ideal correlation, all points would lie on the red line. The grey dashed lines indicate a deviation of ± 25 % from this target value. Fig. 12.a shows the CH₄ correlation, which shows good agreement for most cases, however very strong deviations are present for the O₂ tests. Overall, 55 % of all tests lie within the margin of ± 25 %. Dufour et al. [21] also found a linear correlation between CH₄ and benzene as well as a close to linear correlation of C₂H₄ and total tars when conducting pyrolysis-gasification experiments of biomass in a tubular reactor. They indicate that these correlations can be used in gasification reactors for online tar

Fig. 11. Correlation between a) GC tars (excl. benzene) and CH₄, b) GC tars (excl. benzene) and H₂ and c) GC tars (excl. benzene) and temperature T₄. The linear fit does not consider case O₂/S ER = 0.23 for all cases.

prediction using a FTIR analysis. A strong correlation between CH₄ and tars was also found by Benedikt et al. [22], however, they also report an even more cohesive correlation of C₂H₄ and state it would be the best indicator to predict the tar content.

When looking just at the permanent gases, Benedikt et al. [22] find H₂ to have the strongest correlation regarding the tar content, which was also observed in this study. Results of the H₂ correlation are shown in Fig. 12.b, whereat for 66% of the cases a result within the error margin of 25% was achieved. Additionally, the H₂ correlation shows much better results for the tests using a mixture of steam and oxygen, which makes it more versatile. However, this might not be a general trend as the temperature profile in the reactor changes significantly in our case when adding oxygen. Combustion of char and producer gas (including H₂) in the bottom of the reactor leads to a hot bed region. In our special case, this results in a decrease of electrical heating and therefore a colder

Fig. 12. Evaluation of tar correlations using a) CH₄, b) H₂ and c) temperature.

freeboard which diminishes tar cracking. Therefore, further investigation especially with the focus on gasification plants closer to commercial application is necessary. Furthermore, this correlation shows the best agreement with measurements obtained using Miscanthus as feedstock. Compared to the idealized conditions in this study where homogenous fuel pellets were used, this can be a huge benefit in industrial plants where bigger changes in feedstock can occur. Therefore, a correlation with little influence of fuel composition can be very useful.

Figure 12.c shows the results when applying the temperature correlation to the experimental data set obtained in this study. This

correlation showed the highest coefficient of determination R^2 of 0.83 for the linear fit, which is also reflected by the fact that 67 % of all tests lie within the margin of ± 25 %. Good agreement can be seen for all cases. Contrary to the correlations based on permanent gases, the temperature correlation also leads to very good results for the tests using O₂. However, the influence of fuel composition is stronger compared to the two other correlations.

Although the accuracy of the presented method might not be as good as for conventional offline tar measurement methods and stronger deviations will occur when running the facility at different or new operation conditions, correlations similar to the ones presented can be beneficial as they allow the possibility to react fast and do not come with the need of additional expensive equipment. Furthermore, the technique is suitable for long term operation without operator supervision.

The best correlation may be specific for each plant and has to be found in an individual measurement campaign for a specific unit. In the case of the lab scale reactor used in this study, the correlation based on temperature shows best results which is probably due to the big influence of the freeboard, in other reactors however, the bed region may be more important. Analyzing the comprehensive data set obtained for this study, we give a broader overview about correlations for tar prediction based on quantities which are easy to measure. Gas components, which allow easy online measurement, can lead to good correlations based on CH₄ or H₂. A combination of different correlations also including temperature-based tar prediction can be an even better approach by calculating an averaged estimate of the tar content. An experimental test conducted at reference conditions which was not used when establishing the correlations lead to a CH₄ content of 6.6 vol%db, a H₂ content of 36.5 vol%db and a temperature of 781 °C at T₄. This leads to a predicted tar content of 8.2, 6.7 and 8.7 g/m³ for the corresponding correlation respectively. Employing the average of the three estimates of 7.9 g/m³ shows good agreement with the measured gravimetric tar content of 7.7 g/m³.

As seen in Fig. 12, the correlation based on CH₄ shows strong deviations when employing steam-oxygen mixtures and the temperature based correlation is not very accurate when using a different type of fuel. This information gained during the calibration campaign should also be used to justify the choice of the employed correlation and needs to be considered to exclude correlations in certain cases when using an average of different correlations. The results presented in this study provide a deeper insight on online tar estimation based on permanent gases and temperature. A broader range of conditions presented in literature so far shows that applicable correlations can be found even when operation conditions change significantly. However, it was also found that some correlations are limited especially when oxygen is added to the steam used as fluidizing agent. In the future, also tar prediction based on artificial neural networks like the one developed by Serrano and Castelló [43] will probably be applicable with high accuracy in order improve the operation of gasification facilities.

4. Conclusions

As the cleaning requirements of the producer gas obtained by fluidized bed biomass gasification due to tar contamination is still the most important challenge regarding its application, a fast and easy tar monitoring system in gasification facilities is crucial. In order to allow online monitoring and the ability of instantaneous intervention with the gasification process, different possibilities of tar prediction based on correlations between gravimetric tar and permanent gases or temperature were investigated in this study. A comprehensive set of experimental data obtained during the operation of a bubbling fluidized bed biomass gasifier over several years was used in order to derive accurate and flexible linear correlations to predict the tar content using simple measurement equipment. The best correlation using permanent gases was found for H₂, whereas a slightly worse but still useful correlation was found for CH₄. CO₂ and CO showed no clear tendencies regarding

the tar content of the gas. However, the best correlation was found using the freeboard temperature, which showed good tar predictions for a temperature range from 700 to 800 °C, different fluidizing agents and varying feedstock. Similar correlations based on CH₄, H₂ and temperature were found when the tar content of a representative selection of the samples was determined via GC-MS. In general, a single correlation which works well for certain cases may not work for other ones, as seen in the case of the CH₄ correlation which performs bad for steam-oxygen mixtures with this reactor. As shown in this study, using just permanent gases for tar prediction proposed previously in literature has limitations when a broad range of operating conditions are considered. However, these limitations might be overcome by simply combining it with correlations based on temperature. In order to use a tar prediction method of this kind in an industrial plant, a calibration measurement is indispensable. However, the fact that Benedikt et al. [22] found similar correlations for a bigger pilot plant and for an industrial plant with similar designs leads to the conclusion that even if such correlations are not universally valid for different facilities, correlations with similar principles can be derived for a specific gasifier when adjusted with a measurement campaign. It also needs to be emphasized that the position of the temperature measurement needs to be determined carefully. In order to achieve the most flexible and accurate method of tar prediction, a combination of temperature and permanent gases might look most promising, as they balance each other's weaknesses.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lukas Berg: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - original draft. **Gernot Pongratz:** Investigation. **Aleksandr Pilatov:** Investigation. **Hernán Almuina-Villar:** Investigation. **Christoph Hochenauer:** Project administration, Supervision. **Robert Scharler:** Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing - review & editing. **Andrés Anca-Couce:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement number 731101 (BRISK II). We further want to thank Michaela Riese for conducting the GC analysis at Technische Universität Berlin.

References

- Masson-Delmotte V, Zhai P, Pörtner H-O, Roberts D, Skea J, Shukla PR, et al. Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change. IPCC 2018.
- Anca-Couce A, Hochenauer C, Scharler R. Bioenergy technologies, uses, market and future trends with Austria as a case study. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2021;135: 110237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110237>.
- Molino A, Chianese S, Musmarra D. Biomass gasification technology: the state of the art overview. *J Energy Chem* 2016;25(1):10–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2015.11.005>.
- Sansaniwal SK, Pal K, Rosen MA, Tyagi SK. Recent advances in the development of biomass gasification technology: a comprehensive review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2017;72:363–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.038>.
- Karl J, Pröll T. Steam gasification of biomass in dual fluidized bed gasifiers: a review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2018;98:64–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.09.010>.
- Schmid JC, Benedikt F, Fuchs J, Mauerhofer AM, Müller S, Hofbauer H. Syngas for biorefineries from thermochemical gasification of lignocellulosic fuels and residues—5 years' experience with an advanced dual fluidized bed gasifier design. *Biomass Convers Biorefin* 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-019-00486-2>.
- Benedikt F, Schmid JC, Fuchs J, Mauerhofer AM, Müller S, Hofbauer H. Fuel flexible gasification with an advanced 100 kW dual fluidized bed steam gasification pilot plant. *Energy* 2018;164:329–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.08.146>.
- Benedikt F, Fuchs J, Schmid JC, Müller S, Hofbauer H. Advanced dual fluidized bed steam gasification of wood and lignite with calcite as bed material. *Korean J Chem Eng* 2017;34(9):2548–58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11814-017-0141-y>.
- Meng F, Ma Q, Wang H, Liu Y, Wang D. Effect of gasifying agents on sawdust gasification in a novel pilot scale bubbling fluidized bed system. *Fuel* 2019;249: 112–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2019.03.107>.
- Campoy M, Gómez-Barea A, Vidal FB, Ollero P. Air-steam gasification of biomass in a fluidised bed: process optimisation by enriched air. *Fuel Process Technol* 2009;90 (5):677–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2008.12.007>.
- Chi J, Yu H. Water electrolysis based on renewable energy for hydrogen production. *Cuihua Xuebao/Chinese J Catal* 2018;39(3):390–4. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1872-2067\(17\)62949-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1872-2067(17)62949-8).
- Valderrama Rios ML, González AM, Lora EES, Almazán del Olmo OA. Reduction of tar generated during biomass gasification: a review. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2018;108: 345–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2017.12.002>.
- Kirnbauer F, Wilk V, Kitzler H, Kern S, Hofbauer H. The positive effects of bed material coating on tar reduction in a dual fluidized bed gasifier. *Fuel* 2012;95: 553–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2011.10.066>.
- Kuba M, Fürsatz K, Janisch D, Aziaba K, Chlebeda D, Lojewska J, et al. Surface characterization of ash-layered olivine from fluidized bed biomass gasification. *Biomass Convers Biorefinery* 2021;11(1):29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-020-00863-2>.
- Soria-Verdugo A, Von Berg L, Serrano D, Hochenauer C, Scharler R, Anca-Couce A. Effect of bed material density on the performance of steam gasification of biomass in bubbling fluidized beds. *Fuel* 2019;257:116118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2019.116118>.
- Fuentes-Cano D, von Berg L, Diéguez-Alonso A, Scharler R, Gómez-Barea A, Anca-Couce A. Tar conversion of biomass syngas in a downstream char bed. *Fuel Process Technol* 2020;199:106271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2019.106271>.
- Heidenreich S, Foscolo PU. New concepts in biomass gasification. *Prog Energy Combust Sci* 2015;46:72–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2014.06.002>.
- Neef JPA, Knoef HAM, Zielke U, Sjöström K, Hasler P, Simell PA, et al. Guideline for Sampling and Analysis of Tar and Particles in Biomass Producer Gases 1999.
- Brage C, Yu Q, Chen G, Sjöström K. Use of amino phase adsorbent for biomass tar sampling and separation. *Fuel* 1997;76(2):137–42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-2361\(96\)00199-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-2361(96)00199-8).
- Zachl A, Buchmayr M, Gruber J, Anca-Couce A, Scharler R, Hochenauer C. Flame ionization detection as a simple real-time tar monitoring device for biomass downdraft gasification. *Fuel* 2021;289:119950. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2020.119950>.
- Dufour A, Masson E, Girods P, Rogaume Y, Zoulalian A. Evolution of aromatic tar composition in relation to methane and ethylene from biomass pyrolysis-gasification. *Energy Fuels* 2011;25(9):4182–9. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ef200846g>.
- Benedikt F, Kuba M, Schmid JC, Müller S, Hofbauer H. Assessment of correlations between tar and product gas composition in dual fluidized bed steam gasification for online tar prediction. *Appl Energy* 2019;238:1138–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.01.181>.
- Borgmeyer J, Behrendt F. On-line tar monitoring using light-induced fluorescence: a setup for continuous operation in a biomass gasification plant environment. *Opt Laser Technol* 2020;123:105906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2019.105906>.
- Ren J, Cao J-P, Zhao X-Y, Yang F-L, Wei X-Y. Recent advances in syngas production from biomass catalytic gasification: a critical review on reactors, catalysts, catalytic mechanisms and mathematical models. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2019;116: 109426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109426>.
- Bates RB, Ghoniem AF, Jablonski WS, Carpenter DL, Altantzis C, Garg A, et al. Steam-air blown bubbling fluidized bed biomass gasification (BFBBG): multi-scale models and experimental validation. *AIChE J* 2017;63(5):1543–65.
- Rapagnà S, Jand N, Kienemann A, Foscolo PU. Steam-gasification of biomass in a fluidised-bed of olivine particles. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2000;19:187–97. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534\(00\)00031-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534(00)00031-3).
- Kuba M, Hofbauer H. Experimental parametric study on product gas and tar composition in dual fluid bed gasification of woody biomass. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2018;115:35–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2018.04.007>.
- Myrén C, Hörmell C, Björnbom E, Sjöström K. Catalytic tar decomposition of biomass pyrolysis gas with a combination of dolomite and silica. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2002;23(3):217–27. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534\(02\)00049-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534(02)00049-1).
- Mayerhofer M, Mitsakis P, Meng X, De Jong W, Spliethoff H, Gaderer M. Influence of pressure, temperature and steam on tar and gas in allothermal fluidized bed gasification. *Fuel* 2012;99:204–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2012.04.022>.
- Pfeifer C, Koppatz S, Hofbauer H. Steam gasification of various feedstocks at a dual fluidised bed gasifier: impacts of operation conditions and bed materials. *Biomass Convers Biorefinery* 2011;1(1):39–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-011-0007-1>.
- Herguido J, Corella J, Gonzalez-Saiz J. Steam gasification of Lignocellulosic residues in a fluidized bed at a small pilot scale. Effect of the type of feedstock. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 1992;31(5):1274–82.
- Kuba M, Havlik F, Kirnbauer F, Hofbauer H. Influence of bed material coatings on the water-gas-shift reaction and steam reforming of toluene as tar model compound

- of biomass gasification. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2016;89:40–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2015.11.029>.
- [33] Schmid M, Beirrow M, Schweitzer D, Waizmann G, Spörl R, Scheffknecht G. Product gas composition for steam-oxygen fluidized bed gasification of dried sewage sludge, straw pellets and wood pellets and the influence of limestone as bed material. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2018;117:71–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2018.07.011>.
- [34] Gómez-Barea A, Leckner B. Modeling of biomass gasification in fluidized bed. *Prog Energy Combust Sci* 2010;36(4):444–509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2009.12.002>.
- [35] Gil J, Corella J, Aznar MP, Caballero MA. Biomass gasification in atmospheric and bubbling fluidized bed: effect of the type of gasifying agent on the product distribution. *Biomass Bioenergy* 1999;17(5):389–403. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534\(99\)00055-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0961-9534(99)00055-0).
- [36] Narváez I, Orfó A, Aznar MP, Corella J. Biomass gasification with air in an atmospheric bubbling fluidized bed. Effect of six operational variables on the quality of the produced raw gas. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 1996;35(7):2110–20. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie9507540>.
- [37] Horvat A, Kwapinska M, Xue G, Rabou LPLM, Pandey DS, Kwapinski W, et al. Tars from fluidized bed gasification of raw and Torrefied *Miscanthus x giganteus*. *Energy Fuels* 2016;30(7):5693–704. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.6b00532>.
- [38] Carapellucci R, Giordano L. Steam, dry and autothermal methane reforming for hydrogen production: a thermodynamic equilibrium analysis. *J Power Sources* 2020;469:228391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2020.228391>.
- [39] Li C, Suzuki K. Tar property, analysis, reforming mechanism and model for biomass gasification-An overview. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2009;13(3):594–604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2008.01.009>.
- [40] Salinero J, Gómez-Barea A, Fuentes-Cano D, Leckner B. The effect of using thermocouples on the char particle combustion in a fluidized bed reactor. *Fuel* 2017;207:615–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2017.06.085>.
- [41] Fuentes-Cano D, Gómez-Barea A, Nilsson S, Ollero P. The influence of temperature and steam on the yields of tar and light hydrocarbon compounds during devolatilization of dried sewage sludge in a fluidized bed. *Fuel* 2013;108:341–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2013.01.022>.
- [42] Katsaros G, Pandey DS, Horvat A, Almansa GA, Fryda LE, Leahy JJ, et al. Gasification of poultry litter in a lab-scale bubbling fluidised bed reactor: impact of process parameters on gasifier performance and special focus on tar evolution. *Waste Manag* 2019;100:336–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.09.014>.
- [43] Serrano D, Castelló D. Tar prediction in bubbling fluidized bed gasification through artificial neural networks. *Chem Eng J* 2020;402:126229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.126229>.